

Title: Cover crop effects on carbon sequestration and yield in varied climate scenarios

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Agricultural fields represent both a great opportunity for climate change mitigation through soil carbon sequestration and an uncertain prospect under future climate scenarios. Cover crops have been shown to increase soil organic carbon content over time, and may improve resiliency of fields to increasingly likely weather extremes. However, their performance when intercropped with a cash crop is less studied than sequential applications. We investigated the impacts of intercropping cover crops with cereal oat and autumn rye cash crops in varied climate scenarios, focusing on the cash crop yield and field-level carbon cycle, including net fluxes and soil carbon stocks. We calibrated the STICS soil-crop model over two growing seasons (July 2022 - July 2024) using continuous eddy covariance fluxes, chamber flux measurements, and yield observations from an experimental farm on mineral soil in Southern Finland. We then simulated several cropping scenarios including different cover crops such as Italian ryegrass (shallow rooting), clover (shallow rooting and nitrogen fixing), and fescue (deep rooting), alongside varied meteorological conditions. The change in soil carbon stock and net ecosystem exchange will be evaluated alongside the effects on yield, particularly concerning yield stability and resilience to extreme weather conditions. These simulations and modelling capability can influence monitoring, reporting, and verification systems as well as planning and policy decisions related to future agricultural land management, especially the role of cover crops in agricultural carbon sequestration.